

Synthesis of Some New Derivatives of Azlactone (Part I)

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Manuscript received 19 June 1980, revised 15 December 1980, accepted 7 June 1982

Hippuric acid azlactone (I) was condensed with aldehydes to give the corresponding arylidene azlactones (II). Compounds (II) were reacted with hydrazine hydrate, phenylhydrazine and hydroxylamine to give the corresponding pyrazolines, phenylpyrazolines and isoxazolines, respectively.

In view of bacteriostatic^{1,2} and fungicidal activities of azlactone, we undertook the synthesis of a heterocyclic system containing an azlactone ring condensed with pyrazoline, N-phenyl pyrazoline, and isoxazolines hoping that these compounds might exhibit enhanced bacteriostatic activity. The hippuric acid azlactone (I) was condensed with aldehydes in presence of piperidine as a basic catalyst to give the corresponding arylidene azlactone (II).

The structure of compounds (II) was confirmed by elemental analysis and ir spectra, which showed a carbonyl stretching frequency at 1802 cm^{-1} , characteristic for five-membered rings³ and a band at 1640 cm^{-1} for $\text{C}=\text{C}$.

The additive property of the exocyclic $\text{C}=\text{C}$ in compounds (II) conjugated with the carbonyl group prompted us to investigate their behaviour towards the action of hydrazine hydrate, phenyl hydrazine and hydroxylamine hydrochloride. Interaction of II with hydrazine hydrate under suitable condition gave a variety of pyrazolines. Hydrazine hydrate interacted with II in dioxan giving unstable pyrazolines but when these were treated with glacial acetic acid or when the reaction was carried out in presence of glacial acetic acid, the stable N-monoacetyl pyrazoline (III) was obtained.

The structure of compounds (III) has been established by elemental analysis and ir spectra which showed absorption bands at 1687-1613 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{N}$) and at 1250-1227 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}-\text{N}$) and the absence of the $-\text{NH}$ stretching frequency.

Phenylhydrazine reacted with II in presence of a basic catalyst. The reaction was carried out in dioxan in presence of piperidine giving N-phenyl pyrazolines (IV).

The structure of compounds (IV) was established by elemental analysis and ir spectra which showed absorption bands at 1608-1592 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{N}$) and at 1242-1220 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}-\text{N}$). Compound (IV) proved to be stable on boiling with a mixture of acetic acid and conc. sulphuric acid at room temperature or on heating above its melting point which is the condition that causes the cyclization of phenylhydrazines to pyrazolines. The prepared pyrazoline gave a colour test characteristic for aryl pyrazolines^{5,6}.

The isoxazoline (V) was obtained when a mixture of compound (II) and hydroxylamine in dioxan was refluxed in presence of NaOH. The structure of compounds (V) was established by elemental analysis and ir spectra which showed an absorption band at 1688-1612 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{N}$).

The prepared compounds (III), (IV) and (V) were tested against two bacteria, *B. subtilis* and *E. coli*, and a fungus *Aspergillus*. It was found that the compounds were more active than the parent compound (II).

Fig. 1.

Experimental

Infra red spectra were determined in KBr pellets on an Unicam Sp. 2006 Infrared spectrophotometer. Melting points are uncorrected. Hippuric acid and hippuric acid azlactone⁹ were prepared by known methods.

TABLE 1—ARYLIDINE AZLACTONE (II)

Ar	Yield %	m. p. °C	M. F.	Analysis % Found (Calcd.)		
				C	H	N
C ₆ H ₅	70	120.3	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₂ N	76.91 (77.10)	4.11 (4.42)	5.70 (5.62)
<i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	73	127.9	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₂ N	72.15 (72.45)	4.18 (4.15)	5.14 (5.28)
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	75	132.5	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂	64.91 (65.31)	3.44 (3.40)	9.74 (9.52)
<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	71	137.9	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₂ N	72.05 (72.45)	4.20 (4.15)	5.20 (5.23)

TABLE 2—N-ACETYL PYRAZOLINE (III)

Ar	Yield %	m. p. °C	M. F.	Analysis % Found (Calcd.)		
				C	H	N
C ₆ H ₅	50	160.3	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂	70.75 (70.82)	4.89 (4.92)	13.70 (13.77)
<i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	55	158.9	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂	67.00 (67.29)	4.70 (4.67)	12.95 (13.08)
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	60	164.6	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₂	61.69 (61.71)	4.05 (4.00)	16.02 (16.00)
<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	60	168.9	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂	67.20 (67.29)	4.69 (4.67)	13.12 (13.08)

TABLE 3—PHENYL PYRAZOLINE (IV)

Ar	Yield %	m. p. °C	M. F.	Analysis % Found (Calcd.)		
				C	H	N
C ₆ H ₅	59	140.4	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ ON ₂	77.80 (77.88)	5.05 (5.01)	12.29 (12.39)
<i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	62	158.9	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂	74.27 (74.37)	4.75 (4.79)	11.90 (11.83)
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	63	141.2	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂	68.70 (68.75)	4.20 (4.17)	14.56 (14.58)
<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	60	160.2	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂	74.31 (74.37)	4.80 (4.79)	11.80 (11.83)

TABLE 4—ISOXAZOLINE (V)

Ar	Yield %	m. p. °C	M. F.	Analysis % Found (Calcd.)		
				C	H	N
C ₆ H ₅	65	170.3	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂	72.63 (72.73)	4.60 (4.55)	10.65 (10.61)
<i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	60	167.3	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂	68.51 (68.57)	4.30 (4.29)	10.01 (10.00)
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	63	175.7	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₂	60.20 (60.19)	3.50 (3.45)	13.20 (13.17)
<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	60	180.1	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂	68.49 (68.57)	4.25 (4.29)	10.01 (10.00)

TABLE 5—ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY

Comp.	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>E. Coli</i>	<i>Aspergillus</i>
II	+	+	+ve
III	+++	++	+ve
IV	++	++	+ve
V	+++++	+++++	+ve

Arylidine azlactone (II): Equimolar amounts (0.1 mole) of hippuric acid azlactone and aromatic aldehyde were refluxed in dioxan (25 ml) containing piperidine (1 ml) for 1 to 3 hr. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool and arylidene azlactone was precipitated with petroleum ether (80-100). The product was filtered off, washed several times with petroleum ether and crystallized from ethanol. The results are given in Table 1.

N-Acetyl pyrazoline (III): A mixture of arylidene azlactone (II) (0.1 mole) hydrazine hydrate (0.1 mole) and a few drops of glacial acetic acid in dioxan (25 ml) was heated under reflux for 3 hr. The reaction mixture concentrated when the N-acetyl pyrazoline separated. It was filtered and recrystallized from benzene. The results are listed in Table 2.

N-Phenyl pyrazoline (IV): Equimolar amounts of arylidene azlactone (II) and phenyl hydrazine were refluxed in dioxan (30 ml) containing a few drops of piperidine for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool and the N-phenyl pyrazoline was precipitated with petroleum ether. The product was filtered washed several times with petroleum ether (80-100) and crystallized from the same solvent. The results are listed in Table 3.

Isoxazoline (V): A mixture of arylidene azlactone (II) (0.1 mole), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.1 mole) and a few pellets of NaOH in dioxan (30 ml) was heated under reflux for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered and the precipitate washed thoroughly with dioxan. The isoxazoline was precipitated from the filtrate by ether. The product was filtered, washed several times with ether and recrystallized from the benzene. The results are listed in Table 4.

Biological testing: The bacteria used for testing were *B. subtilis* (gram positive) and *E. coli* (gram negative). The fungus used for testing was *Aspergillus*. The data are listed in Table 5.

References

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